

Paralympic Games: Movement and Progression from Early Stage to Contemporary Era

¹Chitra Bhar, ²Dr. Laden Lepcha

¹Research Scholar, ²Assistant Professor
Department of Physical Education
University of Kalyani, WB, 741235, India

Abstract-

Introduction: Paralympic Games is an International Games for people with different disabilities. In 1960 Ludwig Guttman organized the ninth International Stoke Mandeville Games which was originally started for World War II veterans was considered as the first Paralympic Games. The game has been improved tremendously over the time and held once in four years like as Olympic Games.

Objective: The focus of the research was to highlight that fact, that how the Paralympic Games have been progressed and has changed the attitudes of people with disabilities, increase mobility and accessibility and ensure that person with disabilities have equal opportunities to sports.

Findings: The finding shows that the number of participating countries, number of events, competitions has been increased over a period of time. Many new games have been added in Paralympic Games. The number of participating countries, events and athletes which were 23, 8 and 400 respectively in 1960 has been stands at 162, 22, 4333 respectively in 2020. There were only eight events i.e.-Archery, Athletes, Dartchery, Snooker, Swimming, Table tennis, Wheelchair basketball, Wheelchair fencing in the first Paralympic Game which has risen to twenty two events.

Conclusion: Many para-athletes have been motivated by the inclusion of new events, as a result, the number of total participating countries, events, athletes and winning medals has been increased overall.

Key words: Paralympic, Progression, Movement, Disabilities.

Introduction

One of the most well-known sporting competitions geared toward people with physical disabilities is the Paralympics. The Paralympics feature a variety of sports, including archery, athletics, boccia, cycling (road & track), equestrian, football 5-a-side, football 7-a-side, goalball, judo, powerlifting, rowing, sailing, shooting, swimming, table tennis, sitting volleyball, wheelchair basketball, wheelchair tennis, wheelchair fencing, wheelchair rugby, paracanoe, badminton, and taekwondo, among others. There are two different kinds of Paralympics: summer and winter, both of which are held right away after every four years.

Historical aspects of Paralympic movement

Sir **Ludwig Guttman**, a well-known individual, leading character, in charge of planning the Paralympic games and creating a successful Paralympic movement.

At the time, it served the objective of helping the numerous military soldiers and citizens who had sustained wounds during World War II. At the Stoke Mandeville Hospital in Great Britain, Dr. Ludwig Guttman established a spinal injury center in 1944 at the British government's request. Over time, rehabilitative sport progressed into recreational sport and finally competitive sport. In 1960 Rome, Italy, edition of the Stoke Mandeville Games, which featured 400 athletes from 23 nations, later evolved into the Paralympic Games. They have since happened every four years.

The first Paralympic Winter Games were held in Sweden in 1976, and like the Summer Games, events occur every four years and feature an Opening Ceremony and a Closing Ceremony. Additionally in 1960, the World Federation of Ex-Servicemen established an International Working Group on Sport for the Disabled to research the challenges facing athletes with disabilities. The International Sport Organisation for the Disabled (ISOD), which provided chances for athletes who could not affiliate with the International Stoke Mandeville Games (vision impaired, amputees, people with cerebral palsy, and paraplegics), was born as a result of this in 1964.

When ISOD first began, 16 nations were involved with it, and the organization worked very hard to get athletes who were blind or had limbs amputated into the 1976 Paralympics in Toronto as well as athletes with cerebral palsy into the 1980 Paralympics in Arnhem. Its purpose was to serve as a co-coordinating committee and to accept all future impairments. However, several international organizations focused on people with disabilities were established in

1978 and 1980, including the International Blind Sports Federation (IBSA) and the Cerebral Palsy International Sports and Recreation Association (CPISRA).

The "International Co-coordinating Committee Sports for the Disabled in the World" (ICC) was established in 1982 when the four international organizations realized the necessity to coordinate the Games.

The ICC was originally composed of the four presidents of CPISRA, IBSA, ISMGF and ISOD, the general secretaries and one additional member (in the beginning it was the Vice-President, and later on the Technical Officer).

The International Committee of Sport for the Deaf (CISS) and International Sports Federations for Persons with an Intellectual Disability (INAS-FID) joined in 1986, but the deaf still maintained their own organisation. However, the member nations demanded more national and regional representation in the organisation.

Finally, on 22 September 1989, the [International Paralympic Committee](#) was founded as an international non-profit organisation in Dusseldorf, Germany, to act as the global governing body of the Paralympic Movement.

Methodology

This chapter contain design of the study and procedure of collection of the data.

Design of the study-

According to the necessity and nature of the study, a survey method was designed to analyse the progression of Paralympic game and its movement.

Secondary Sources-

Data were collected basically from secondary sources i.e. Internet, Journals and Wikipedia with key notes- Paralympic, Progression, Movement.

The progression of Paralympic Movement informed :

- Enhancement of total number of participating countries.
- Increasing total number Athletes.
- Increment of total number of medal winning countries.

Result and discussion

World Para Athletics provided 10 eligible impairment types which includes Eight physical impairment (Impaired muscle power, Impaired passive range of movement, Limb deficiency, Leg length difference, Short Stature, Hypertonia, Ataxia, Athetosis,) One vision impairment and One Intellectual impairment.

Table-1 Classification Rules And Regulations Track And Jump Events

Discipline	Sports Classes	Impairment Types
Running and jumping (20 classes)	T11-13	Vision impairment (Damage optical nerve, Visual cortex of brain)
	T20	Intellectual impairment (Limitation in cognitive function and adaptive behaviour)
	T35-38	Co-ordination impairments hypertonia, ataxia and athetosis (Hypertonia diminish muscle flexibility, Ataxia related to uncoordinated movement, Athetosis related to slow movement)
	T40-41	Short stature (Shorter upper and lower limb)
	T42-44	Lower limb competing without prosthesis affected by limb deficiency, leg length difference, impaired muscle power or impaired passive range of movement
	T45-47	Upper limb/s affected by limb deficiency, impaired muscle power or impaired passive range of movement
	T61-64	Lower limb/s competing with prosthesis affected by limb deficiency and leg length difference
Wheelchair racing (7 classes)	T32-34	Co-ordination impairments hypertonia, ataxia and athetosis (Hypertonia diminish muscle flexibility, Ataxia related to uncoordinated movement, Athetosis related to slow movement)
	T51-54	Limb deficiency, leg length difference, impaired muscle power or impaired passive range of movement

Race Running (3 classes)	RR1	Hypertonia athletes with severe co-ordination impairment
	RR2	Ataxia athletes with severe co-ordination impairment
	RR3	Athetosis athletes with severe co-ordination impairment

Table-1 represents Track and Jump event, athlete required to undergo three different sports discipline which classified 30 different sports classes. Sports classes T11-13 classified as vision impairment which include damage optical nerve or visual cortex of brain, retinitis pigmentosa and diabetic retinopathy. Sports classes T20 classified as intellectual impairment who have an intellectual disability experience limitations in their cognitive functioning and adaptive behaviour. Before the age of 18, this impairment must exist. Sports classes T35-38 and RR1, RR2, RR3 represents Hypertonia, Ataxia and Athetosis. Hypertonia increase muscle tension and diminish muscle flexibility due to damage to the central nervous system. Sportspeople who have ataxia experience uncoordinated movements as a result of CNS injury and Cerebral palsy, traumatic brain injury, stroke, and multiple sclerosis. Athetosis causes athletes to move slowly and uncontrollably all the time. Sports classes T40-41 represents short stature which indicate the bones in the upper limbs, lower limbs, and/or trunk are shorter. T42-44 lower limb affected and T45-47 upper limb affected by leg length difference, limb deficiency and impaired muscle. In wheel chair racing T51-54 represents limb deficiency, leg length difference and impaired muscle power.

Table-2 Classification Rules And Regulations of Throwing Events

Discipline	Sports Classes	Impairment Types
Standing throws (19 classes)	F11-13	Vision impairment (Damage optical nerve, Visual cortex of brain)
	F20	Intellectual impairment (Limitation in cognitive function and adaptive behaviour)
	F35-38	Co-ordination impairments hypertonia, ataxia and athetosis (Hypertonia diminish muscle flexibility, Ataxia related to uncoordinated movement, Athetosis related to slow movement)
	F40-41	Short stature (Shorter upper and lower limb)
	F42-44	Lower limb competing without prosthesis affected by limb deficiency, leg length difference, impaired muscle power or impaired passive range of movement
	F45-46	Upper limb/s affected by limb deficiency, impaired muscle power or impaired passive range of movement
	F61-64	Lower limb/s competing with prosthesis affected by limb deficiency and leg length difference
Seated throws (11 classes)	F31-34	(Co-ordination impairments (hypertonia, ataxia and athetosis)
	F51-57	Limb deficiency, leg length difference, impaired muscle power or impaired range of movement

Table-2 represents Field event, athlete required to undergo two different sports discipline which classified thirty classes. Sports classes F11-13 classified as vision impairment which include damage optical nerve or visual cortex of brain, retinitis pigmentosa and diabetic retinopathy. F20 classified as intellectual impairment who have an

intellectual disability experience limitations in their cognitive functioning and adaptive behaviour. Before the age of 18, this impairment must exist. Sports classes F35-38 represents Hypertonia, Ataxia and Athetosis. Hypertonia increase muscle tension and diminish muscle flexibility due to damage to the central nervous system. Sportspeople who have ataxia experience uncoordinated movements as a result of CNS injury and Cerebral palsy, traumatic brain injury, stroke, and multiple sclerosis. Athetosis causes athletes to move slowly and uncontrollably all the time. Sports classes F40-41 represents short stature which indicate the bones in the upper limbs, lower limbs, and/or trunk are shorter. F42-44 lower limb deficiency, F45-46 upper limb and F61-64 lower limb deficiency. Leg Length difference has a disparity in their leg length as a result of trauma or a disruption in limb growth. Athletes with limb deficiencies have completely missing or partially missing bones or joints as a result of injury (such as traumatic amputation), disease (such as amputation caused by bone cancer), or congenital limb deficiencies (such as dysmelia). A restriction or absence of passive mobility in one or more joints characterizes athletes with impaired passive range of motion.

Table-3 Total number of participating Countries, Sports, Events and Athletes in Paralympic from 1960 to 2021

YEAR	HOST CITY	COUNTRY	PARTICIPATING COUNTRIES	TOTAL NO. OF SPORTS	TOTAL NO. OF EVENTS	NO. OF ATHLETES
1960	Italy	Rome	23	8	57	400
1964	Tokyo	Japan	21	9	144	375
1968	Tel Aviv	Israel	29	10	181	750
1972	Heidelberg	Germany	43	10	187	984
1976	Toronto	Canada	38	13	447	1657
1980	Arthem	Netherlands	42	12	489	1973
1984	New York & Stoke Mandeville	USA & UK	86	18	903	2900
1988	Seoul	South Korea	61	16	732	3057
1992	Barcelona & Madrid	Spain	157	16	487	4620
1996	Atlanta	USA	104	20	508	3259
2000	Sydney	Australia	122	20	551	3881
2004	Athens	Greece	135	19	517	3808
2008	Beijing	China	146	20	472	3951
2012	London	UK	164	20	503	4237
2016	Rio	Brazil	159	21	528	4011
2021	Tokyo	Japan	162	22	539	4333

Table-3 represents total sixteen paralympic games which were started in 1960 in Italy at Rome with 23 participating countries, 8 sports, 57 events and 400 athletes. Day by day number of participating countries, sports, events athletes were increased. Last 16th Paralympic was organized at Tokyo in Japan with 162 participating countries, 22 sports, 539 events and 4333 athletes.

Figure 1 Graphical representation of total Participating Countries

Note: Figure is based on the number of countries participating in Paralympic from 1960 to 2021

Figure 2 Graphical representation of total number of Game

Note: Figure is based on the total number of games introduced in Paralympic Game

Figure 3 Graphical representation of total number of Events

Note: Figure is based on total events conducted in Paralympic Game

Figure 4 Graphical representation of total number of athlete

Note: Figure is based on total number of athlete participated in Paralympic Game

Table-4 Total number of Medal(Gold, Silver and Bronze) received in Paralympic

YEAR	TOTAL MEDAL	GOLD	SILVER	BRONZE
1960	268	106	85	77
1964	419	144	138	137
1968	576	189	186	201
1972	575	188	187	200
1976	1173	447	378	348
1980	1118	456	353	309
1984	2780	978	951	851
1988	2203	732	730	741
1992	1051	370	338	343
1996	1574	517	516	541
2000	1657	550	549	558
2004	1568	519	517	532
2008	1431	473	471	487
2012	1522	503	503	516
2016	1597	529	529	539
2021	1668	539	540	589

Table 4 represents total medal list i.e - Gold, Silver and Bronze. In 1960 first organized Paralympic game, there were a total number of 268 medals out of which 106 gold, 85 silver and 77 bronze. The number of medals was highest in 1984 where the total number of medals was 2780, out of which 978 gold, 951 silver and 851 bronze. In 2020 total number of medal was 1668 out of which 539 gold, 540 silver and 589 bronze.

Figure 5 represent total medal list of Paralympic game

Note: Figure is based on total number of medals including gold medals, silver medals and bronze medal

Discussion on the findings

The Paralympic game classified into two groups which were- 1.Track and Jump events and 2. Throwing events. Track and Jump events were further classified into three disciplines according to the impairment types of the athletes which were Running and jumping discipline, Wheelchair Racing and Race Running and on the other hand Throwing events were classified into two events which were Standing Throw and Seated Throw.

There were twenty (20), seven(7) and three(3) sports classes include in Running and jumping discipline, Wheelchair racing and Race running discipline respectively. The sports classes include in Running and Jumping discipline were T11-13, T-20, T35-38, T40-41, T42-44, T45-47 and T61-64 according to the types of impairment. In wheelchair Racing discipline there were 7 sports classes which were T32-34 and T51-54 respectively. Similarly in Race Running there were three sports classes which were RR1, RR2 and RR3.

There were nineteen (19) and eleven (11) sports classes in Standing throw and Seated throw discipline. The different sports classes in standing throw were F11-13, F20, F35-38, F40-41, F42-44, F45-46 and F51-57 .Seated throw were F31-34 and F51-57.

The number of athletes in 1960 Paralympic were 400 which held in Rome and where 23 number of countries had participated in the following years the Paralympic was hosted by Japan, Israel, Germany, Canada and Netherlands from the year 1964 to 1980 where the number of athletes reached from 375 to 1973. From the year 1988 to 2021 Paralympic Game was hosted by USA, South Korea, Spain, USA, Australia, Greece, China , UK, Brazil and Japan where the number of athlete were 4333 in the year 2021. The number of participating countries increased from 23 into the year 1960 to 162 in the year 2021. Along with the participating countries the total number of Sports and Events were eventually increased from 57 events to 539 events and number of sports increased from 8 sports to 22 sports from the year 1960 to 2021.

Conclusion

In 1960 first Paralympic game was started with 23 participating countries, 400 athletes and 8 games i.e Archery, Athletics, Dartchery, Snooker, Swimming, Table tennis, Wheelchair basketball, Wheelchair fencing. After that the number of participating countries, athletes, games have increased time to time and two games i.e-Weight lifting and Lawn bowls were included and total number of games were ten in the year 1968. U.S.A organized Paralympic for two times in 1984 and 1996. The highest number of athlete participated in 1992 hosted by Spain. Total number of 164 countries participated in 2012 London Paralympic game which was highest participating countries. In 2020 Paralympic game was canceled due to pandemic situation as Corona virus attack in worldwide and it was postponed to 2021. The Paralympic which was hosted in 2021, at Tokyo in Japan, there were 162 participating countries, 22 sports, 539 events and 4333 athletes. Total number of 22 sports were Archery, Athletics, Boccia, Cycling(Road &

Track), Equestrian, Football 5-a-side, Football 7-a-side, Goalball, Judo, Powerlifting, Rowing, Sailing, Shooting, Swimming, Table tennis, Sitting Volleyball, Wheelchair basketball, Wheelchair tennis, Wheelchair fencing, Wheelchair rugby, Paracanoe, Badminton, Taekwondo.

In 1960 first Paralympic game Athletes received total 268 medals out of which 106 Gold, 85 Silver and 77 Bronze medals. Total 2780 medals were received in 1984, which was highest number of medals received by athletes. In 2021 Japan hosted Paralympic game where total medals were 1668 out of which 539 gold, 540 silver and 589 bronze.

The number of participating countries and total athletes were increased as the total number of games were increased. The number of participating countries and athletes were 23 and 400 in 1960, but now these number stand at 162 and 4333 respectively which shows the progression of Paralympic movement.

REFERENCES:

1. Rome 1960, International Paralympic Committee (IPC)
2. ^ "Summer Games Governance 1960 to 1992", IWAS
3. ^ "Beijing Paralympics factsheet", BBC, July 11, 2008
4. ^ "Participation Numbers: Rome 1960 Paralympic Games", International Paralympic Committee
5. ^ IPC searchable database
6. ^ "Paralympic Games History", Channel Four Paralympics
7. ^ Paralympic Games Open At Rome Olympics Site, St. Petersburg Times, September 19, 1960, Google News Archive Search
8. ^ <https://www.paralympic.org/sdms4/hira/web/participantNumbers/rome-1960>
9. *"The History of the Paralympic Movement". Inside the Games website. Retrieved 4 March 2015.*
10. ^ "About Us". *International Paralympic Committee website. Retrieved 4 March 2015.*
11. ^ Jump up to:^{a b c d e f g h i j k l m n o p q r s t u} "25-year anniversary of the IPC". *International Paralympic Committee website. Retrieved 10 March 2015.*
12. ^ Jump up to:^{a b c d e f g h i j k l m n o p q r s t u v w} "The IPC to rebrand the 10 sports it acts as International Federation for" (Press release). *International Paralympic Committee. 30 November 2016. Retrieved 13 December 2016.*
13. ^ The Paralympian, International Paralympic Committee (IPC)
14. ^ Jump up to:^{a b} IPC-IOC Co-operation, The official website of the International Paralympic Committee
15. ^ International Sports Federations, International Paralympic Committee (IPC)
16. ^ Contacts - International Sports Federations (IFs), International Paralympic Committee (IPC)
17. Darcy, S. (2012). Doping, boosting and other forms of cheating at the Paralympics. *The Conversation*, 9. <http://theconversation.com/doping-boosting-and-other-forms-of-cheating-at-the-paralympics-9228> [Google Scholar]
18. IPC. (2018). *International Paralympic Committee - Annual Report 2018*. [https://www.paralympic.org/sites/default/files/2019-10/2018 IPC Annual Report 2018.pdf](https://www.paralympic.org/sites/default/files/2019-10/2018%20IPC%20Annual%20Report%202018.pdf) [Google Scholar]
19. Olympic game museum <https://www.olympic-museum.de/index.html>
20. IPC historical database <https://www.paralympic.org/results/historical>